

THE ROLE OF SELF-PORTRAIT IN PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE FINE ARTS TEACHERS

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Abstract. *This article is about the past, future of the portrait (self-portrait) genre, which is considered one of the main genres of visual art in the professional training of future visual art teachers in the pedagogical higher education system, and its role in the professional training of young people in the continuing education system. the word goes.*

Keywords: *art, cultural heritage, creator, thinking, imagination, creativity, style, form, image.*

INTRODUCTION

In the current era, the fate of our development is decided by spiritually mature people. In this regard, it is considered as one of the most priority areas related to the improvement of society and the prospects of young people, and special attention is paid to the education of the young generation. At the same time, the initiative of the head of our state put forward "Increasing the attention to our youth, involving them in culture, art, physical education and sports, forming the skills of using information technologies in the youth, the youth of our country The first item of the 5 important initiatives "on promotion of reading, ensuring women's employment" among young people, that is, to increase the interest of young people in music, painting, literature, theater and other types of art. It is assumed that it will serve to bring out the taste - it puts responsible tasks before us, the specialists of visual arts.

Fine art appeared and developed on the basis of human labor, beliefs, and religious views. It is an elegant form of art that combines painting, sculpture, graphics, and illuminates the spiritual image of a person and the content of his interactions with others. Sometimes it creates non-existent images, which are the product of the artist's imagination, and reflects different periods in human history.

During the reign of Great Amir Temur, full conditions were created for the development of all types and genres of fine art. At the initiative of Amir Temur personally, portrait and anamalistic genres developed in Central Asia. During the Timurid period, the ancient art and science of Uzbekistan developed to an unprecedented level.

During this period, painters such as K. Behzod, M. Muzakhib, A. Bukhari, M. Samarkandi created. An art school - Academy was formed in Herat under the leadership of Alisher Navoi, the sultan of poetry, and under the leadership of Behzod. All genres of painting flourished during this period.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Portrait is one of the oldest genres of painting, which reveals the external and internal experiences of people through images.

If we look into the distant past, we can see the first examples of portraits as works of art in ancient Egypt. The genre of portraiture has been developing for many years, and specific requirements and tasks have appeared in different periods.

In painting a portrait, the artist must use all his knowledge and skills and be able to accurately find the specific mental state of the person he is portraying. We know many masters of the portrait genre from the history of world fine art. The works of the great artists of the

Renaissance - Leonardo da Vinci, Raphael, Veronese, Tintoretto - still inspire lovers of painting to admire their skill in expressing the complex emotions of a person in their delicate portraits. In each portrait, not only the external likeness, but also the inner spiritual world of a person - intellectual, full of feelings, noble features - were able to be depicted in a highly artistic, unique style.

In art, a portrait embodies not only the external uniqueness of an individual, but also the special and unique appearance of a person with his inner world. In painting a portrait, the artist must use all his knowledge and skills and be able to accurately find the specific mental state of the person he is portraying.

People's artist of Uzbekistan, academician Malik Nabiev is a talented artist who can interpret the image of great figures in his own way. His portrait "Amir Temur" (photo 1) is proof of our opinion. He skillfully described the state of the great commander sitting on the throne, thoughtfully, with his hands on the hilt of the sword. It is convincingly shown that he carefully observes the peace of the country and the well-being of the people. The royal crown on his head fits his figure very well. His extremely strictness, bravery and intelligence, and his intelligence are reflected in his face.

Similarly, the great thinker, scientist Abu Rayhan, while creating a portrait of Beruni, describes him as a humble and simple person. The feelings of wisdom, insight and creative enthusiasm are visible in his eyes (Fig. 2).

M. Nabiev was widely sought after, relying on the opinions of oriental scientists, on the basis of facts and instructions, he deeply studied the historical period in which Beruni lived, and he was a great encyclopedic scientist, he studied various sciences of his time - astronomy, physics, mathematics, geodesy, who thoroughly mastered the basics of geology and mineralogy, Abu Rayhan Beruni was portrayed in a picture.

Fig. 1. Portrait of Amir Temur.

Fig. 2. Portrait of Beruni

RESEARCH RESULTS

Self-portrait is a unique genre of portrait. Self-portrait (Greek autos - self, French portrait - image) - a type of portrait. In a self-portrait, an artist or sculptor depicts himself. Usually, when working on a self-portrait, the author uses a mirror or several mirrors, shows his personality (image) in the work, expresses his nature, inner world, creative philosophy. Self-portrait has existed since ancient times and was widely developed in antiquity, the Middle Ages, and especially during the Renaissance. Many self-portraits were created in times when the desire to reveal the human psyche and spiritual world intensified. Self-portraits of Renaissance artists: Raphael, Leonardo da Vinci, Rembrandt, Dürer, Van Dyck, Bryullov are famous.

In the visual art of Uzbekistan, self-portrait began to spread widely in the 20s and 30s of the 20th century. A. Volkov, A. Siddiqi, B. Hamdamov, A. Abdullaev and others also created self-portraits.

In this genre, many professors, teachers, masters and students of the Faculty of Arts of Navoi State Pedagogical Institute are working in this genre, participating in many competitions and improving their skills. In particular, famous scientists, masters and young students participated with their creative works in the Self-Portrait exhibition held in the gallery of the Navoi Regional Branch of the Art Academy of Uzbekistan's Union of Artists in Navoi (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. From the self-portrait exhibition

CONCLUSION

The portrait genre of fine art expresses the spiritual image of a person.

In our opinion, the role of self-portrait in the professional training of future creative artists is incomparable. Because, one of the most complex genres of visual art is depicting the human face, which requires an artist to be a master of shapes, proportions and colors, and to have a good understanding of a person's personality, to be able to perceive his mental state, his emotions. he should be able to see them, the facial tension, the color of the face should match the state of the painting, he should also have the skills to realistically express the changes in the heart of the person, the mental excitement, because the work shows the person in the picture, who he is, his age, his actions - he should show his habit, title, even body structure, wealth and poverty.

To sum up, fine art is aimed at illuminating the life of the people and the qualities of the artist.

The visual art of Uzbekistan is in sync with the processes taking place in the world community, and is characterized by the fact that every artist strives to express his views and experiences in new styles and forms.

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